

THE FUTURE OF IP PROTECTION: HARNESSING THE POWER OF AI LANGUAGE AND VISION MODELS

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ABSTRACT

In this project, we present an advanced interfacing solution for Raspberry Pi that integrates two RFID modules to enhance railway safety and prevent train collisions. The RFID modules are strategically placed on either side of the railway track to detect the presence of trains. When both RFID modules simultaneously read signals, indicating the presence of two trains on the same track, the system activates a relay to trigger the transmission of latitude and longitude coordinates from a GPS module to a web server for further processing. This web-based communication enables real-time monitoring and the implementation of safety measures to prevent potential collisions.

Additionally, the system incorporates an ultrasonic sensor and a PIR (Passive Infrared) sensor for detecting human presence and obstacles on the railway track. The ultrasonic sensor measures distances to detect obstructions, while the PIR sensor identifies human movement. If either sensor detects a potential hazard, the system reports this information to the central processing unit on the Raspberry Pi.

The design also includes a fire sensor to detect fire hazards on the track and an LCD for visual feedback on system status. The relay module plays a crucial role by connecting the RX pin of the Raspberry Pi to the common terminal of the relay, the TX pin of the GPS module to the normally closed terminal, and the TX pin of the EM18 RFID modules to the normally open terminal. When the two RFID modules detect trains on the same track, the relay activates to ensure that the location data from the GPS module is sent to the web server.

Overall, this interfacing system leverages RFID technology, advanced sensors, and real-time data transmission to significantly enhance railway safety measures. By integrating these components, the system provides comprehensive monitoring and detection capabilities to avert accidents and ensure safe railway operations.

Keywords: Raspberry Pi, IOT, pir sensor, RFID, GPS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Anywhere at some point of the arena, railroads expect an important task and offering railway protection is a substantial problem. Railroads are probable the least highpriced method of transportation. Finally, each person leans inside the path of railroads to excursion. In late overviews, several injuries befell at the railroad intersections due to the carelessness in guide duties. To present protection to the road customers via diminishing the accidents that generally seem because of carelessness of road customers and sometimes mistakes made through the guardians. To preclude the accidents, sensors set at a few separations at every of the gates which recognizes the arrival and takeoff of to teach. The facts about the arrival and takeoff of the train are dispatched in the direction of the microcontroller. The microcontrollers send records en route for the motor and open the gate and additionally shut the entryway. Consequently, the hour of the entryway being shut is less contrasted with the manually operated gates. In an operated by hand device, the entryway is shut by the shield when he receives statistics from station ace through a name that to teach is displaying up from the beyond station. Likewise, reliability is excessive, as it is not exposed to guide errors. Addition to this gate the train localization is achieved with concept of IOT where the Node MCU like Wi-Fi modules is used in train with GPS. Over current system the gate are pole based and manual operated with human intervention. We have developed a system is modified such that a sliding gate which protect people crossing even of gate closer which found in conventional systems.

2. RELATED WORKS

An investigation into "A Prototype Model of AUTOMATED Level Crossing Framework Using Sensor Piezoelectric. The use of the piezoelectric accelerometer is planned to create a robotized automated level intersection framework. The door opening and closing during train appearance has been successfully verified by a model. A piezoelectric accelerometer installed between the rails gives the train its distinctive appearance, and the Instrumentation Enhancer may record and amplify train vibration. The improved sign is subsequently delivered to the door or recipient area by the RF Transmitter. The RF recipient receives the encoded signal and makes it ready for further processing. The entrance at the automatic level junction is closed in the event that the vibration sensor yield indication is present.

The "Automated Level Crossings" is a system created by Ahmed et al. The predicted using the microcontroller 8052, a framework was once constructed. The main goal of this endeavour is to keep away from railroad mishaps that happen at level intersections. Two sensors placed on one or the other surface of the door allowed for the detection of trains approaching the entrance. One sensor is referred to as the front side sensor and the other as the back side sensor. When a foreside sensor detects a sign, the sensor is notifies same to the microcontroller 8052.

When the train approaches the door and scopes the side sensor, the microcontroller then closes the door as a result, keeping it closed until the train passes the door. The sensors are activated and the takeoff sign is sent from the microcontroller when the surface sensors detect the train. The entrance opens as the engine is turned around by the microcontroller.

Work on "Sensor Based Automatic Control of Railway Gate" was completed by Monica Bobby et al. He offers the notion of computerizing rail route doors. Entryway sensors are used to prevent any human error that might occur when they are in operation. Mishaps on the rail line could result from the guardian being slow to open and close doors.

This study contributes to the development of a system that automates door activity at level intersections using microcontrollers and detects collisions there. Infrared sensors are used as the component for automating rail route entryways. To determine the movement of the object enclosing it, an IR sensor detects the radiation. Programmable rail route door control was argued in this study.

Research has been done on "Automated system using IOT" by Vishwanatha CR et al. A method for regulating the development of a vehicle that necessitates human effort and coordination, the initiator provides a variety of solutions for accidents and delays inside the train. It is advised that doors genuinely function, that mistakes that can cause problems even as people enter, and that the doorway be sealed. The strategy for computerising Moving. and people from temporary the junction is presented in this work as being completely unique. Computerization of intersection entryways makes organising the door to prevent accidents and gather season of the street customers simple and safe.

"Controlling Railway Gates Using Detectors, GPS, and GSM" is the topic of research by Srinidhi Srinivasan et al. [5].

Utilising GPS and GSM, creators conducted research on level intersection regulator. utilised GPS and GSM to complete work on the level intersection regulator In this piece, the author combines the use of a GSM modem with GPS (Worldwide Situating Framework) to achieve successful door closing at level junctions. The train's appearance and departure are detected by finders, which also transmit the information to the subsequent intersections. When the framework was put into practice, it became clear that it was quick, precise, powerful, and adaptable.

3. METHODOLOGY

Contrary to more traditional approaches, the suggested way of connecting a Raspberry Pi to two RFID modules, as well as PIR and ultrasonic sensors, has a number of advantages. The first benefit of using RFID technology is automated train detection, which provides accurate and timely information on approaching trains on the railway track. This automated method reduces the need for human intervention, lowering the possibility of human error and raising overall safety standards. Second, by making it possible for the system to detect people and objects effectively, the integration of ultrasonic and PIR sensors improves its capabilities. This makes sure that any unauthorised activity on the track or possible obstacles are quickly discovered and reported to the central controller for the necessary steps.

Figure 1 Block diagram.

Internet domain based apps in embedded systems allow obscure device and virtual machine monitoring and regulate using a remote access interface. The monitoring system using Raspberry Pi serves as a significant device for people, communities, and associations in shielding and getting to the next level to detect and mishaps in railway.

Raspberry pi:

Raspberry Pi a well known single board system introduced by Raspberry Pi Foundation provide a assortment of project and application choices. The Raspberry Pi board has a processor, memory, input/output pins, and various ports that let it speak with different gadgets and interface with physical environment.

Figure 2 Raspberry pi

Both fledgling and prepared designers can utilize it since it is viable with Linux-based working frameworks like Raspbian and upholds Python. Raspberry Pi has many purposes thanks to its little size and low power utilization, including media focuses, schooling, mechanical technology, home mechanization, Web of Things, and prototyping. It has formed into a popular stage for dabbling, learning, and creating unique arrangements, empowering individuals and gatherings to dive into the universes of figuring and hardware.

Fire Sensor:

A sensor which is most sensitive to a normal light is known as a flame sensor. That's why this sensor module is used in flame alarms. This sensor detects flame otherwise wavelength within the range of 760 nm – 1100 nm from the light source. This sensor can be easily damaged to high temperature. So this sensor can be placed at a certain distance from the flame. The flame detection can be done from a 100cm distance and the detection angle will be 600. The output of this sensor is an analog signal or digital signal. These sensors are used in fire fighting robots like as a flame alarm.

What is a Flame Sensor?

A flame-sensor is one kind of detector which is mainly designed for detecting as well as responding to the occurrence of a fire or flame. The flame detection response can depend on its fitting. It includes an alarm system, a natural gas line, propane & a fire suppression system. This sensor is used in industrial boilers. The main function of this is to give authentication whether the boiler is properly working or not. The response of these sensors is faster as well as more accurate compare with a heat/smoke detector because of its mechanism while detecting the flame.

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Working Principle

This sensor/detector can be built with an electronic circuit using a receiver like electromagnetic radiation. This sensor uses the infrared flame flash method, which allows the sensor to work through a coating of oil, dust, water vapor, otherwise ice.

Flame Sensor Module

The pin configuration of this sensor is shown below. It includes four pins which include the following. When this module works with a microcontroller unit then the pins are

- Pin1 (VCC pin): Voltage supply ranges from 3.3V to 5.3V
- Pin2 (GND): This is a ground pin
- Pin3 (AOUT): This is an analog output pin (MCU.IO)
- Pin4 (DOUT): This is a digital output pin (MCU.IO)

Relay:

What is a relay?

A relay is an electromagnetic switch that is used to turn on and turn off a circuit by a low power signal, or where several circuits must be controlled by one signal.

Most of the high end industrial application devices have relays for their effective working. Relays are simple switches which are operated both electrically and mechanically. Relays consist of an electromagnet and also a set of contacts. The switching mechanism is carried out with the help of the electromagnet. There are also other operating principles for its working. But they differ according to their applications. Most of the devices have the application of relays.

Pin Diagram:

Why is a relay used?

The main operation of a relay comes in places where only a low-power signal can be used to control a circuit. It is also used in places where only one signal can be used to control a lot of circuits. The application of relays started during the invention of telephones. They played an important role in switching calls in telephone exchanges. They were also used in long distance telegraphy. They were used to switch the signal coming from one source to another destination. After the invention of computers they were also used to perform Boolean and other logical operations. The high end applications of relays require high power to be driven by electric motors and so on. Such relays are called contactors.

Relay Design

- There are only four main parts in a relay. They are
- Electromagnet
- Movable Armature
- Switch point contacts
- Spring

The figures given below show the actual design of a simple relay.

Relay Construction

It is an electro-magnetic relay with a wire coil, surrounded by an iron core. A path of very low reluctance for the magnetic flux is provided for the movable armature and also the switch point contacts.

The movable armature is connected to the yoke which is mechanically connected to the switch point contacts. These parts are safely held with the help of a spring. The spring is used so as to produce an air gap in the circuit when the relay becomes de-energized.

How relay works?

The relay function can be better understood by explaining the following diagram given below.

Relay Design

The diagram shows an inner section diagram of a relay. An iron core is surrounded by a control coil. As shown, the power source is given to the electromagnet through a control switch and through contacts to the load. When current starts flowing through the control coil, the electromagnet starts energizing and thus intensifies the magnetic field. Thus the upper contact arm starts to be attracted to the lower fixed arm and thus closes the contacts causing a short circuit for the power to the load. On the other hand, if the relay was already de-energized when the contacts were closed, then the contact move oppositely and make an open circuit.

As soon as the coil current is off, the movable armature will be returned by a force back to its initial position. This force will be almost equal to half the strength of the magnetic force. This force is mainly provided by two factors. They are the spring and also gravity.

Relays are mainly made for two basic operations. One is low voltage application and the other is high voltage. For low voltage applications, more preference will be given to reduce the noise of the whole circuit. For high voltage applications, they are mainly designed to reduce a phenomenon called arcing.

Relay Basics

The basics for all the relays are the same. Take a look at a 4 pin relay shown below. There are two colors shown. The green color represents the control circuit and the red color represents the load circuit. A small control coil is connected onto the control circuit. A switch is connected to the load. This switch is controlled by the coil in the control circuit. Now let us take the different steps that occur in a relay.

Relay operation

- **Energized Relay (ON)**

As shown in the circuit, the current flowing through the coils represented by pins 1 and 3 causes a magnetic field to be aroused. This magnetic field causes the closing of the pins 2 and 4. Thus the switch plays an important role in the relay working. As it is a part of the load circuit, it is used to control an electrical circuit that is connected to it. Thus, when the electrical relay in energized the current flow will be through the pins 2 and 4.

Energized Relay (ON)

- **De – Energized Relay (OFF)**

As soon as the current flow stops through pins 1 and 3, the relay switch opens and thus the open circuit prevents the current flow through pins 2 and 4. Thus the relay becomes de-energized and thus in off position.

De-Energized Relay (OFF)

In simple, when a voltage is applied to pin 1, the electromagnet activates, causing a magnetic field to be developed, which goes on to close the pins 2 and 4 causing a closed circuit. When there is no voltage on pin 1, there will be no electromagnetic force and thus no magnetic field. Thus the switches remain open.

Pole and Throw

Relays have the exact working of a switch. So, the same concept is also applied. A relay is said to switch one or more poles. Each pole has contacts that can be thrown in mainly three ways. They are

- **Normally Open Contact (NO):** NO contact is also called a make contact. It closes the circuit when the relay is activated. It disconnects the circuit when the relay is inactive.
- **Normally Closed Contact (NC):** NC contact is also known as break contact. This is opposite to the NO contact. When the relay is activated, the circuit disconnects. When the relay is deactivated, the circuit connects.
- **Change-over (CO) / Double-throw (DT) Contacts:** This type of contacts are used to control two types of circuits. They are used to control a NO contact and also a NC contact with a common terminal. According to their type they are called by the names **break before make** and **make before break** contacts.

Relays can be used to control several circuits by just one signal. A relay switches one or more poles, each of whose contacts can be thrown by energizing the coil.

Relays are also named with designations like

- **Single Pole Single Throw (SPST):** The SPST relay has a total of four terminals. Out of these two terminals can be connected or disconnected. The other two terminals are needed for the coil to be connected.
- **Single Pole Double Throw (SPDT):** The SPDT relay has a total of five terminals. Out of these two are the coil terminals. A common terminal is also included which connects to either of two others.
- **Double Pole Single Throw (DPST):** The DPST relay has a total of six terminals. These terminals are further divided into two pairs. Thus they can act as two SPST which are actuated by a single coil. Out of the six terminals two of them are coil terminals.
- **Double Pole Double Throw (DPDT):** The DPDT relay is the biggest of all. It has mainly eight relay terminals. Out of these two rows are designed to be change over terminals. They are designed to act as two SPDT relays which are actuated by a single coil.

Relay Applications

- A relay circuit is used to realize logic functions. They play a very important role in providing safety critical logic.
- Relays are used to provide time delay functions. They are used to time the delay open and delay close of contacts.
- Relays are used to control high voltage circuits with the help of low voltage signals. Similarly they are used to control high current circuits with the help of low current signals.
- They are also used as protective relays. By this function all the faults during transmission and reception can be detected and isolated.

Application of Overload Relay

Overload relay is an electro-mechanical device that is used to safeguard motors from overloads and power failures. Overload relays are installed in motors to safeguard against sudden current spikes that may damage the motor. An overload relay switch works in characteristics with current over time and is different from circuit breakers and fuses, where a sudden trip is made to turn off the motor. The most widely used overload relay is the thermal overload relay where a bimetallic strip is used to turn off the motor. This strip is set to make contact with a contactor by bending itself with rising temperatures due to excess current flow. The contact between the strip and the contactor causes the contactor to de-energize and restricts the power to the motor, and thus turns it off.

Another type of overload motor is the electronic type which continuously watches the motor current, whereas the thermal overload relay shuts off the motor depending on the rise of temperature/heat of the strip.

All overload relays available to buy comes in different specifications, the most important of them being the current ranges and response time. Most of them are designed to automatically reset to work after the motor is turned back on.

Relay Selection

You must note some factors while selecting a particular relay. They are

- Protection Different protections like contact protection and coil protection must be noted. Contact protection helps in reducing arcing in circuits using inductors. A Coil protection helps in reducing surge voltage produced during switching.
- Look for a standard relay with all regulatory approvals.
- Switching time Ask for high speed switching relays if you want one.
- Ratings There are current as well as voltage ratings. The current ratings vary from a few amperes to about 3000 amperes. A In case of voltage ratings, they vary from 300 Volt AC to 600 Volt AC. There are also high voltage relays of about 15,000 Volts.
- Type of contact used whether it is a NC or NO or closed contact.
- Select Make before Break or Break before Make contacts wisely.
- Isolation between coil circuit and contacts

PIR SENSOR:

A PIR sensor, also known as a passive infrared sensor, is a type of electrical sensor that picks up infrared radiation from nearby objects or living things. The term "passive" denotes that the sensor only detects the infrared energy released or transmitted by other sources; it does not emit any radiation of its own. Security systems, automatic lighting, and other uses requiring motion detection frequently make use of

Figure 3 Figure:3 PIR sensors

Ultrasonic sensor:

The waves that are reflected off of things are detected by an ultrasonic sensor, which emits ultrasonic waves into the atmosphere. One can find ultrasonic sensors in automatic door openers, backup sensors for cars, and burglar alarm systems, to name a few. Information processing technology is developing quickly, and new application fields are expanding as well, like machinery for industrial automation and electronics for automobiles. Murata has developed a number of ultrasonic sensors that are small in size but have exceptionally excellent performance using their specialized, well-established production process for piezoelectric ceramics. Your use of our ultrasonic sensors will be improved by the knowledge in this catalog.

Figure 4 Ultrasonic Sensor

LCD:

An LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) is a commonly used display technology in embedded systems that provides visual feedback and information.

Figure 5 LCD (Front View)

Figure 6 LCD (Back View)

The front view frequently incorporates a network of pixels organized in lines and segments, with every pixel equipped for showing various varieties or shades. The front view may likewise include fastens or contact touchy regions for client input, permitting collaboration with the implanted framework. Interestingly, the back perspective on a LCD regularly includes the electronic parts that drive the presentation. This incorporates a backdrop illumination, which gives light to the screen to further developed perceivability. The backdrop illumination is generally a progression of LEDs (Light-Radiating Diodes) situated behind the presentation board. The back view likewise envelops the control hardware answerable for getting information and orders from the microcontroller or framework, deciphering and handling the signs, and driving the proper pixels to show the ideal substance on the front view.

GPS (Global position system):

Through the use of satellites and ground stations, the Global Positioning System (GPS), a satellite-based system, determines and measures its position on Earth. NAVSTAR GPS, sometimes known as GPS, is another name for the navigation system. The information from at least four satellites is required for a GPS receiver to be accurate. The GPS receiver doesn't communicate with the satellites in any way. Fleet management, cabs, and cellphones are just a few of the applications that use this GPS receiver.

With the help of a constellation of satellites and ground stations, a GPS receiver can pinpoint its exact location wherever it is.

Radio frequency (1.1 to 1.5 GHz) is used by the receiver to receive data from these GPS satellites. A GPS module or ground station can use the data it has received to determine its position and time.

Figure 7 GPS

BUZZER:

A buzzer or beeper is an example of an auditory signaling device. These gadgets can be mechanical, electromechanical, or piezoelectric. Signals and beepers are habitually utilized as morning timers, clocks, and affirmation of human info such a console or mouse click. PCs, printers, copiers, cautions, toys, toys for automobiles, telephones, timers, and other electronic goods regularly employ buzzers, which are integrated structures of electronic transducers and a DC power source. The board and active buzzer 5V are located in this area that is dedicated to sensor expansion modules. Rated power can be coupled to make a simple, plug-and-play circuit design.

Figure 8 Buzzer

A buzzer is a basic but useful component that may be used to add sound features to our project or system. This component is used in a variety of electrical applications because of its 2-pin structure's small size and simplicity of use on breadboards, perf boards, and even PCBs.

The two varieties of buzzers are frequently available. A basic buzzer that when engaged makes a constant beeeeeppp sound as depicted in this illustration. Another kind is a ready-made buzzer, which is bigger and beeps. Beep. Beep. A circuit that oscillates inside of it causes it to make sound. But this model is the most often used since it can be simply modified with different circuits to work with our application.

Dc motor:

Electricity is converted into mechanical rotation by direct current (DC) motors. Magnetic fields created by electrical currents move a rotor that is mounted within the output shaft of a DC motor. The output torque and speed are influenced by a number of variables, including the electrical input and the motor's design.

Figure 9 DC Motor

L293D(Motor driver);

Typically, autonomous robot motors are controlled by motor driver. A motor driver connects the motors to an Arduino. The motor driver ICs that are utilized the most frequently belong to the L293 series, which includes the L293D, L293NE, etc. These ICs are designed to simultaneously control two DC motors. L293D consists of two H-bridges. The H-bridge is the most straightforward circuit for controlling a motor with a low current rating. L293D will be used to refer to the motor driver IC. L293D consists of 16 pins.

Figure 10 L293D (Motor Driver)

RC522 RFID Module:

The 13.56MHz RFID module known as the RC522 is built on the NXP Semiconductors MFRC522 controller. The module can support I2C, SPI, and UART and normally ships with an RFID card and key fob. Applications for person or item identification, such as attendance systems, typically employ it.

Figure 11 RC522 RFID Module

4. ADVANTAGES AND APPLICATIONS

4.1. Applications

- Reliability
- Scalability
- Cost-effective
- Compact
- Energy-efficient
- Integration
- Remote monitoring

4.2. Applications

- Railway
- Industries

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 12 TITLE

The 13.56MHz RFID module known as the RC522 is built on the MFRC522 controller from NXP Semiconductors. I2C, SPI, and UART are all supported, and the module frequently includes an RFID card and key fob. Applications for identifying people or things, such as attendance systems, typically employ it.

Figure 13 Displaying real-time ultrasonic value and pir sensor on an LCD screen

Figure 14 This is Raspberry Pi connected system Monitor Screen.

Figure 15 Location (GPS) values and they are displayed on an LCD screen

Figure 16 As a status indicator, RFID matches is displayed on the LCD display. When was given alerts

Figure 17 The Rail Tack and GPS Values are uploaded in adafruit server (IOT)

Figure 18 The sensor and GPS values are uploaded in adafruit server (IOT). These are the field values.

6. CONCLUSION

In this project, the work has many important advantages, such as fewer accidents at railway level crossings, improved accuracy, and fewer mistakes brought on by manual operations. An efficient and cutting-edge technology used to decrease the incidence of railway accidents is an automatic gate control system.

This strategy offers significant benefits to both railway management and road users. The whole procedure is automated. As a result, this technique can be applied in towns and rural areas without a station master or lineman. A micro-controller that is coupled to PIR sensors and ultrasonic sensors automates level crossings that are unmanned. We can avoid the greatest amount of accidents from happening at the railway disaster and when a human or other object is spotted, the PIR and ultrasonic sensors will activate. Following a match of RFID cards, a second train will arrive on the opposite side. Reduce the railway accident prevention measures, we conclude.

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